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Bio-composites based on fungal mycelium and beech particles impregnated with BPCM (bio-phase change material) for thermal energy storage

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ABSTRACT

The building sector is a major contributor to Europe's carbon emissions, and transition to a bio-based economy is essential for achieving long-term sustainability goals. The European Union has set ambitious targets for climate-neutral heating and cooling by 2050, which requires the widespread adoption of energy-efficient and environmentally friendly technologies. A key element in this transition is the integration of fully bio-based materials in construction. While the use of solid wood in building design has made significant progress, there remain substantial opportunities to harness the potential of bio-based materials, especially those that improve thermal performance while minimising environmental impacts.

This research focuses on the development of innovative bio-composite materials that incorporate bio-based phase change materials (bioPCMs) with lignocellulosic (wood) particles bound by fungal mycelia. By exploring the potential of bio-based materials with thermal energy storage capabilities, the study aims to demonstrate how these materials can replace traditional building materials with a high environmental footprint. Specifically, the paper investigates bio-based phase change material derived from renewable sources, which are integrated into bio-composites made from beech particles. The thermal properties of these materials are evaluated to assess their potential for use in sustainable building practices.

This study highlights the feasibility of using bio-based materials not only as structural components but also as functional elements that contribute to thermal regulation in buildings. The results show that bio-composites with integrated bioPCM could serve as viable alternatives to conventional materials, offering both environmental and functional benefits in the pursuit of sustainable, climate-neutral building solutions.

Keywords: agroforestry chain, bio-materials, biological phase change material, lignocellulosic waste, mycelium, wood particles.

1. INTRODUCTION

The concept and transition to a sustainable bio-based economy is non-well defined within the building sector in Europe (apart from building with solid wood and wood derived products such as cross laminated and glue-lam timber) while significantly more should be done to exploit all the opportunities, maximise the cascading use of woody biomass and consider the challenges involved. In the building/construction sector, it is necessary to develop new strategies towards fully bio-based materials with reduced or without any toxic chemicals to be cost-effective and

multifunctional and replace traditional materials with heavy environmental impact. In 2021 the EU adopted its first European Climate Law. It set in stone Europe's goals to become climate-neutral by 2050, as well as a target of 55% less emissions by 2030, in comparison to 1990. As required under the Climate Law, the Commission also recommended, in February 2024, an additional intermediate target of 90% less emissions by 2040, confirming the previous programs. The Green Deal Industrial Plan, which includes the Critical Raw Materials Act and the Net-Zero Industry Act was adopted in February 2023. These Acts create a predictable and simplified regulatory environment in their respective fields of action and will enable the scaling up of manufacturing capacity for the net-zero technologies and products that our economy needs.

The European commission has also laid the groundwork to build a more circular and resource-efficient economy. This is a part of the changes in the EU legislation. All new public buildings must become coal-for-heating neutral by 2027 aiming at implementing the rules for energy efficiency of buildings towards the European Green Deal (EGD). The above imposes a transition to energy efficient building, exclusion of fossil fuels and transition to renewable heat sources to guarantee carbon neutrality of our cities. Bio-based materials from renewable sources have become an inevitable part in building and construction applications. Wood is the most available material for construction industry and thus, use of timber and other wood-based material has experienced growth during the last decade in single and multi-floor buildings, due to the high ratio of strength to density, thus bringing renewability, sustainability and climate benefits (Ramage *et al.* 2017). However, wood has moderate density and specific heat capacity and cannot absorb and store excessive energy inside buildings or control temperature fluctuations in buildings (Mathis *et al.* 2018). To handle this problem with wood and wood-based materials used in construction industry, one promising approach is to incorporate bio-phase change material into wood cells.

The aim of the present study was to reveal the thermal energy storage (TES) properties and chemical reliability of the produced bio-composite involving fungal mycelia as a natural binder. The study was inspired by the increased interest to renewable phase change materials (PCMs) and their ability to save thermal energy and reduces fossil fuel consumption and pollutant emissions (Temiz *et al.* 2020).

2. EXPERIMENTAL METHODS

2.1 Materials

Fungal mycelia of *Ganoderma resinaceum* was obtained in the forest close to Firenze, Italy, and identified by polymerase chain reaction and DNA sequencing. Grain spawn used to grow the fungus *G. resinaceum* consisted of a grains mixture composed of 50% *Panicum miliaceum* (millet), 9% *Phalaris canadiensis*, 20% *Setaria italica*, 20% *Avena sativa*, and 1% soybean oil.

Spruce and beech particles were used for the biocomposites with bioPCM. The particles were impregnated with an organic biological PCM (bioPCM), *i.e.*, from a natural origin and renewable. Untreated spruce and beech particles were used for production of untreated control bio-composites for comparison.

The bioPCM was purchased from Sigma Aldrich, Italy to ensure 95% purity grade. The BPCM chemical name is not mentioned in this for a specific request of participants to the project BIOBUILD, where this study was carried out.

2.2 Impregnation of BPCM in beech fibers

The bioPCM was placed in an oven at 40 °C to melt, while the wood particles were dried at 103 °C for 24 h to remove the moisture. Once the absolute dry weight of the wood particles was

determined, they were placed in a container within an autoclave heated to 40°C to ensure that the bioPCM remains liquid during impregnation. A vacuum of about 250 mbar for 30 min was applied to evacuate the air from the cell lumens. In the next step, a pressure of 6 bar for 1 h was applied to impregnate the bioPCM inside the wood. After impregnation, the pressure was released to normal and the particles left for 1 h in the liquid bioPCM to equalise the pressure. The impregnated wood particles were leached to remove the excessive amount of bioPCM by placing the particles in an oven at 40°C for 24 h. The retention of the bioPCM in the particles was evaluated by the formula:

$$R = \frac{(m_1 - m_0)}{m_0} \times 100 \% \quad (1)$$

where m_0 is the initial mass of the particles, m_1 is the mass of the particles after impregnation.

2.3 Preparation of bio-composites

Both beech and spruce particles represent waste products from the sawmilling. The obtained beech was compressed into briquettes that were hydrated with hot water at 90 °C, amount 1.7% w/w to release the wood particles. Spruce particles were obtained as such. The wood particles were sterilised in an autoclave at 120 °C for 25 min at 1.1 atm pressure of water vapour steam. The impregnated substrates were sterilised by UV rays for 2 h.

The sterilised substrates were mixed under a laminar flow hood as follows:

- beech sawdust: (50% w/w untreated and 50% impregnated with bioPCM);
- Control samples (beech sawdust and spruce sawdust).

In addition, 10% grain spawn obtained on mixed cereal grains was added to each of the combinations above. The mixtures of spawn and wood particles were placed in molds of dimensions 19 × 19 cm and 10 × 10 cm in a climatic room at 25 °C for 25 days. After the exposure the composites were dried at 60 °C for 3 days to block the growth of mycelia.

2.4 Characterisation of panels

The density of the wood composites (Table 1) was evaluated by the ratio of weight at 20 °C and 65% RH, after reaching a constant weight in a conditioning room, and the volume obtained by measurements of the dimensions with a caliper.

T-history method (Nazari *et al.* 2022) was used to monitor the temperature profile of several samples simultaneously over time, illustrating melting/freezing point and degree of supercooling. The samples were thermally insulated using 20 mm thickness insulation material of expanded polyethylene (EPE) foam in identical configuration for all samples including bioPCM impregnated beech particles, non-impregnated particles in the control composite and aluminium control plate. A Rigid box was crafted to fit the sample size (no air between the box and the samples) using the EPE foam panels glued by vinyl glue. T-type thermocouples placed at the centerline and in the middle of the samples were used to record the temperature changes over time. For cold and hot ambient climate, two chambers were employed, the former used for cold ambient climate at 5 °C, while the latter was used for hot ambient climate at 40 °C target temperature. The chamber's temperatures were recorded with two thermocouples. The samples were first cooled down at 5 °C, and then transferred into the chamber at 40 °C and the temperature profiles recorded. Once the equilibrium temperature was reached (after *ca.* 5 h) the samples were transferred back to 5 °C chamber and the temperature changes recorded. The simultaneous five thermocouples' recordings have been made by CR6 Campbell Scientific datalogger (www.campbellsci.com/cr6).

The spectroscopic characterisation of the interaction of the fungus with the bioPCM and wood particles was performed on Petri dishes with agar malt medium by FT-IR analysis.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Impregnation of bio-material

Table 1: Average retention obtained on beech particles impregnated with BPCM of three batches.

Batch	Beech particles (g)	BioPCM (g)	Beech particles impregnated with bioPCM (g)	Retention (R) (%) in according to formula [1]
1	612	1570	1488	143
2	500	1335	1364	165
3	513	961	1326	158
Mean	541.7	1289	1393	155

The impregnation of beech particles was complicated due to the use of large amount of bioPCM to cover the beech particles. It was found that the leaching of the particles after impregnation is an essential technological part to remove the excessive part of the bioPCM and prevent further leaching from the bio-composite.

3.2 Characterisation of biomaterials

Table 2: Dimensions, weight and density of mycelium-bioPCM composite panels (average values and standard deviations in parentheses).

Panels	Dimension (cm)	Weight [g]	Density [g/cm ³]	Substrates
1. AA	9 × 9	63.0	0.452	Untreated beech: bioPCM impregnated beech in ratio 50:50
2. AA	9 × 9	55.6	0.439	Untreated beech: bioPCM impregnated beech in ratio 50:50
3. AA	9 × 9	60.8	0.437	Untreated beech: bioPCM impregnated beech in ratio 50:50
Mean		59.8 (3.8)	0.442 (0.01)	

Figure 1: Bio-composite panels prepared with beech particles impregnated BPCM (top) and without BPCM as controls (bottom).

Fig. 2 shows the changes of the temperature profile in the time for the test samples during the heating and cooling steps. When the samples were transferred from 5 °C to the climate chamber set to 39 °C, the materials' temperature increased from the starting temperature of 5 °C until it

reached the chamber's temperature of 39 °C. During this heating process, a phase change transition was observed for the panels of beech particles impregnated with bioPCM (Fig. 2, the brown line). The figure shows that during both heating and cooling processes, untreated beech sample and aluminium sample reached the equilibrium temperature faster than the composite with the impregnated wood particles. This is due to the improvement in the thermal mass of the composites with bioPCM. The bioPCM has enabled the composites to store thermal energy in terms of latent heat and release the energy in the temperature range of approximately 20-25 °C, *i.e.*, room temperature.

Figure 2: Temperature profiles versus time for the samples during the heating and cooling process of bioPCM beech impregnated and non-impregnated 50:50 (sample BPCM_AA), untreated beech (sample CONTROL_AA) and aluminium sample (AL).

The transition phase peaks of bioPCM-impregnated particles encapsulated by fungal mycelia were weaker compared to those of pure bioPCM, as observed in previous thermal storage studies. Moreover, it can be inferred that bioPCM may not be ideal for fungal mycelium growth (unpublished data, S. Palanti *et al.*). There seems to be an interaction between the bioPCM and fungal mycelia when the bioPCM is impregnated into wooden substrates for the preparation of fungal mycelium panels. To explore this interaction further, a culture of *G. resinaceum* was grown on Scots pine fibers impregnated with bioPCM on Petri dishes.

Figure 3: *G. resinaceum* growth on agar-malt medium (left) and on agar-malt medium with BPCM (right).

FT-IR analysis of the impregnated fibers and the developed fungal growth showed that it was challenging to distinguish the peaks corresponding to the fungus and the bioPCM, as their peaks were in the same wavelength range. By considering the FT-IR peaks of three substances, *i.e.*, the wood, the bioPCM, and the fungus *G. resinaceum* (Fig. 4) and the combination of them, the fungus and impregnated fiber, it became clear that interpreting the weak transition phase peaks was difficult. Further investigation is needed to better understand the interaction between these materials and to explain the observed phenomena.

Below the peaks of the studied components.

G. resinaceum:

- two peaks around always around 2921 and 2853 [cm^{-1}], corresponding to groups C-H;
- band 1700 – 1500 [cm^{-1}], corresponding to amines, constituents of proteins;
- 1400 - 1200 [cm^{-1}], attributable to lipids;
- 1200 - 950 [cm^{-1}], characteristic peak of *G. lucidum* [20];
- 900- 400 [cm^{-1}], carbohydrate characteristic band.

Wood: (Pandeya *et al.* 2023)

- 3350 O-H bond elongation;
- 2911 C-H bond elongation;
- in the region between 1800 and 600 [cm^{-1}], there are the components related to the structure of the cell wall of wood: components aromatics of lignin, hemicellulose and cellulose;
- 925–1145 [cm^{-1}], associated with carbohydrates.

BPCM:

- two peaks around 2921 and 2853 [cm^{-1}], correspond to groups C-H, which is the main skeleton of the bioPCM;
- 1737 [cm^{-1}], corresponding to the esters, present in the structure;
- 1300 - 1000 [cm^{-1}], there are a series of peaks, the most evident attributable to an ether.

Figure 4: a) FT-IR of bioPCM (orange line), Scots pine (green line) and *G. resinaceum* (blue line), b) FT-IR of sample containing *G. resinaceum* and Scots pine fibres impregnated with bioPCM. The blue arrows characteristic peaks of *G. resinaceum*, the red ones possible peaks belonging to the bioPCM.

4. CONCLUSIONS

The panels prepared with wood particles impregnated with bioPCM showed clear ability of thermal storage that can be used in buildings to decrease the use of heating and cooling, thus reaching the recommendation of EGD.

The slight peaks of the transition phase in the mycelia panels could be due to the very low amount of bioPCM in the wood particles, probably below the sensitivity of revealing instrument. The study showed an innovative approach of the use of fungal mycelia as a binder in bio-composites with added functionality, *i.e.* storage and release of thermal energy. The bio-composite is fully bio-based and can be reused or recycled in various way after the end of its service life. The topic needs further investigations as it offers multiple options for future bio-based materials.

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